

MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETINING
JIZZAX FILIALI

**ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION
TADQIQOTLARNING
DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI
VA RIVOJLANISH
TENDENSIYALARI:
YECHIMLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR
RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI
TO'PLAMI**

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THE IMPLEMENTATION OF GRICE'S MAXIMS OF THE COOPERATIVE PRINCIPLE IN COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: The article touches upon the role of the cooperative principle in the process of speech interaction. To succeed participants should take into this principle in the process of speech interaction. On the assumption four categories under one or another of which will fall certain more specific maxims and submaxims that may be distinguished.

Key words: communication; utterance; cognition; cooperative principle; maxims of conversation, implicature.

The functional-cognitive paradigm which occupies an important place in modern linguistics is characterized by such distinctive features as expansionism, anthropocentricity, functionalism and explanationality. One of the areas of linguistic pragmatics along with the study of the pragmatic potential of linguistic units is the study and analysis of the principles of speech interaction as well as the rules and strategies with the help of which this process is carried out. Like any expedient activity, communication activity is subject to the principle of rationality. It means that, a person, wanting to achieve a certain goal, chooses an action that will allow them to achieve this goal faster and with minimal effort and resources. This idea was reflected in the already classic work of Paul Grice "Logic and conversation". The scientist introduced the concept of cooperative principle in his pragmatic theory. This principle is implemented in several postulates that P. Grice calls maxims – the maxim of quantity (be no less or no more than required), the maxim of quality (tell the truth, do not say what you do not have sufficient grounds for), the maxim of relation (be relevant – do not deviate from the topic), the maxim of manner (speak clearly, briefly and consistently) [3].

Compliance with the cooperative principle communication is a kind of "quasi-agreement" which is prescribed for all participants in the process of speech interaction. It is important to note that the participants in this interaction are determined to comply with this principle which is the basis for the implementation of various goals in the communication process.

Analyzing the aforementioned maxims in his work P. Grice notes the fact of the emergence of various doubts about this or that postulate. For example, with regard to the maxim of quantity, he believed that while in general the transmission of superfluous information was not a violation of the principle of cooperation, in some cases such superfluous information could sometimes be misleading, giving rise to

irrelevant questions and considerations; in addition, there may be an indirect effect when the listener is confused by the fact that they suggested the presence of some special purpose, a special sense in transmitting this unnecessary information. The maxim of relation can also sometimes cause difficulties due to the presence of different types and foci of relevance as well as due to possible displacement [Ibid.].

Criticizing Grice's the principle of cooperation researchers have repeatedly attempted to revise the number of maxims and regroup the postulates within the framework of this principle. Theoretically, these categories are absolutely relevant, but in the process of analyzing real speech communication, there is an inevitable need for more detailed classification if necessary [5].

Real human communication is far from the process of perfect communication. Some rules within the framework of the cooperative principle may be violated, but, nevertheless, these violations do not undermine the general principle. This means that the deviation from the rule receives a meaningful interpretation as a kind of implicit meaning that corrects the appearance of the corresponding violation. According to V.V. Bogdanov if the implication at the level of meaning is absent, it would be necessary to question the validity of the cooperative principle itself [1].

The key point of the implicatures theory is that all participants of speech interaction observe the cooperative principle, and if any of the maxims is violated, but the communicator does not avoid cooperation, then the statement contains a hidden, implicit meaning. From this point of view, according to some researchers the communication model is based on the fact that the addressee needs to recognize and reconstruct the intentions of the speaker [3].

In other words, the deliberate creation of implicatures by speakers does not indicate a violation of the cooperative principle, but proves its flexibility. Thus, thanks to the means of implicating information, it becomes possible to achieve a perlocutive effect without generating those statements that would provide this effect. At the same time it should be noted that if the addressee is unable to trace and recognise the given implicature, or vice versa, detecting it where it was not originally laid down can lead to a communicative failure and, as a result, to a state of incompatibility and conflict.

The attitude to the cooperative principle as a universal principle of human communication among modern linguists is rather ambiguous. On the one hand, the cooperative principle can be applied not only to communication, but also to all rational human behaviour. On the other hand, cooperative communication, which means the desire to meet the addressee halfway in achieving their communicative goals, is a rather rare phenomenon in real life. Social and gender characteristics of interlocutors and the type of discourse are important factors recognized by many scientists who question the cooperative principle [2].

Nevertheless, despite many discussions related to the cooperative principle this theory is a kind of project that is constantly expanding, supplemented and revised.

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СПЕЦИФИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОЯЗЫЧНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ РЕЧЕВОГО ОБЩЕНИЯ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ОВЛАДЕНИЯ СОВОКУПНОСТЬЮ КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ ЗНАНИЙ

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена особенностям обучения культуре речи на иностранном языке как компонента формирования иноязычной коммуникативной компетенции. Особое место в этом процессе занимает овладение различными видами знаний – контекстными, интеракционными, языковыми, являющимися совокупностью коммуникативных знаний и механизмов.

Ключевые слова: обучение иностранному языку, иноязычная коммуникативная компетенция, культура иноязычного речевого общения, коммуникативное знание, межкультурное взаимодействие.

В современных реалиях в педагогической практике очевидно прослеживается взаимосвязь между формированием иноязычной компетенцией и овладением культурой речевого общения на иностранном языке. Методика формирования культуры речевого общения опирается на общие дидактические принципы обучения иностранному языку – это означает, что культура речевого общения не изучается отдельно от языка. Методическая наука сформулировала и придерживается положения о взаимосвязанном изучении всех аспектов иностранного языка. Действительно, грамматика языка тесно взаимосвязана со